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Towards single-trial classification of invasively recorded auditory evoked potentials in cochlear implant users

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Abstract

Objective. One promising approach towards further improving cochlear implants (CI) is to use brain signals controlling the device in order to close the auditory loop. Initial electroencephalography (EEG) studies have already shown promising results. However, they are based on noninvasive measurements, whereas implanted electrodes are expected to be more convenient in terms of everyday-life usability. If additional measurement electrodes were implanted during CI surgery, then invasive recordings should be possible. Furthermore, implantation will provide better signal quality, higher robustness to artefacts, and thus enhanced classification accuracy. **Approach.** In an initial project, three additional epidural electrodes were temporarily implanted during the surgical procedure. After surgery, different auditory evoked potentials (AEPs) were recorded both invasively (epidural) and using surface electrodes, with invasively recorded signals demonstrated as being markedly superior. In this present analysis, cortical evoked response audiometry (CERA) signals recorded in seven patients were used for single-trial classification of sounds with different intensities. For classification purposes, we used shrinkage-regularized linear discriminant analysis (sLDA). Clinical speech perception scores were also investigated. **Main results.** Analysis of CERA data from different subjects showed single-trial classification accuracies of up to 99.2% for perceived vs. non-perceived sounds. Accuracies of up to 89.1% were achieved in classification of sounds perceived at different intensities. Highest classification accuracies were achieved by means of epidural recordings. Required loudness differences seemed to correspond to speech perception in noise. **Significance.** The proposed epidural recording approach showed good classification accuracy into sound perceived and not perceived when the best-performing electrodes were selected. Classifying different levels of sound stimulation accurately proved more challenging. At present, the methods explored in this study would not be sufficiently reliable to allow automated closed-loop control of CI parameters. However, our findings are an important initial contribution towards improving applicability of closed auditory loops and for next-generation automatic fitting approaches.

1. Introduction

A cochlear implant (CI) is a device for treatment of individuals with severe to profound hearing loss, in whom the CI replaces the function of the inner ear. It consists of an external sound processor with a transmitting coil, and an implanted portion which

consists of a receiver and an electrode array that allows the transmission of audio signals directly to the spiral ganglion. This set-up enables hearing ability to be restored. Although modern CI systems already allow users to experience speech perception at a fairly high level, this still falls far short of normal hearing abilities, especially in noisy conditions [1–3]. The

sound processor can be programmed with a speech processing strategy and several parameters which are adjusted to each individual patient. Over the years, a wide range of different preprocessing algorithms have been developed in order to aid speech perception in difficult listening situations; these involve, for example, automatic gain control, noise cancellation and beam formers, which are steered by the CI processor and automatic algorithms [1]. Nevertheless, the chief means by which the patient themselves can adjust sensitivity and general loudness level is by manually operating switches or a remote control, which is imprecise and somewhat laborious in everyday-life listening situations. Therefore, independent and adequate control of the CI by the patient will be an important future step. One promising approach towards improving CIs involves the use of brain signals to adjust and control the device.

A system of this kind, chiefly known as a brain-computer interface (BCI), helps to establish communication or motor control when natural pathways are disrupted. Typically, a BCI detects voluntary changes in electroencephalography (EEG) signals and translates different brain states into control signals for different applications which provide feedback to the user. Among electrical brain responses, different approaches to recording can be distinguished. In general, recordings can be conducted either non-invasively or invasively. Signals recorded non-invasively at the scalp (such as EEG signals) have a limited spatial resolution (for details see [4]) when compared to invasively recorded signals which can, for example, be recorded directly at the cortex. This is caused by the scalp, the skull, the cerebrospinal fluid and (finally) the meninges of the brain attenuating the electromagnetic signals created by the neurons. Although the signals are attenuated, EEG is the most commonly used signal acquisition method for BCI systems. By contrast, the various invasive methods that are also used — such as electrocorticography (ECoG), in which small electrodes are placed directly on the surface of the cortex [5, 6], or implanted intracortically [7, 8] — produce very good results. However, as stated in [9], the generators of the evoked potentials have to be targeted more exactly when recording directly onto the cortex.

Research into BCIs initially focused on communication and control - in other words, replacement of lost functions. In recent years, however, BCI systems have also been used to improve, enhance and restore lost function, as for example in stroke rehabilitation, detection of lapses of attention or stimulation of muscles [10]. Here a further promising application is being investigated, namely the use of BCI technology in hearing devices, especially in CIs. One possible use of BCI technology for CI systems might be an automated fitting procedure (see appendix D in [10]) which has already been investigated in [11]. Finke *et al* provided the first evidence that EEG signals

can be automatically classified in CI users, and that this classification has the potential to objectify and automate aspects of the CI fitting procedure. However, this is not the only possible application. BCIs could also provide active and passive [12] control over hearing devices by closing the auditory loop. Active control could entail selection of the preferred listening program without the need of a remote control. A promising approach relevant for active control of a CI is the use of auditory evoked potentials (AEPs). Previous studies have shown the possible suitability of different auditory paradigms [13–15]. Passive control could entail automatic adjustments of a CI in response to the user's cognitive state (reflecting listening effort or loudness experience, for example) as well as identifying auditory attention and target speaker detection [16–19].

However, all of these investigations are based on non-invasive signal acquisition, which requires the use of additional EEG electrodes mounted on the user's scalp. This entails an additional, clearly visible, head montage which may also be uncomfortable for the patient and less robust to artefacts in everyday situations [20]. Signals recorded from the surface of the brain provide better results, but this invasiveness limits acceptance for most BCI applications. Where CIs are controlled by neural activity, however, the electrodes can be implanted together with the CI (which needs to be implanted in any case). Therefore, the use of invasively recorded signals is a promising approach which merits further development.

In our first study in this topic [9, 21, 22], we recently investigated the scope for recording auditory induced neuronal signals via epidural electrodes in CI users. The aim of the study was to obtain insights into how to make future closed-loop CI systems more suitable for day-to-day use. For this reason, the study protocol was based on a small but realistic number of recording channels. Furthermore, only such recording locations as are typically accessible during a CI surgery were selected. For the study we recruited 10 adult patients who were scheduled for cochlear implantation at our department. During surgery on these individuals, who were post-lingually deafened, three additional epidural electrodes were implanted temporarily [9]. With these electrodes, different AEP recordings were performed and compared subjectively and objectively with reference to standard clinical electrode settings recorded simultaneously by using surface electrodes. One of these AEP measurements involved cortical evoked response audiometry (CERA). This is an objective hearing test that records AEPs from the auditory cortex generated in response to sounds introduced into the patients' ears. In essence, the test gives information about the level of sound needed to produce a signal response, and confirms the status of the auditory cortex [23]. We found that the invasive recording approach was feasible, safe and well tolerated

by patients [9]. A visual evaluation of the invasively recorded cortical evoked response audiometry by experienced audiologists revealed clearer N100 waves, which were also visible at lower stimulation intensities than when standard clinical surface electrodes were used. Furthermore, there was less signal interference related to artefacts. In addition to subjective evaluation, we performed objective quality investigations which also showed significantly better signal quality for the invasive data compared to the scalp recordings.

The aim of the present work is, by performing classification analyses on the CERA data, to get one step nearer to closing the auditory loop based on data acquisition methods suitable for use in everyday life (figure 1). A closed-loop system of this nature has various applications in CI users, including active and passive CI adaptation and control, automated fitting of the implant, and CI evaluation in children [9, 11]. For our purpose we use a subset of the data obtained in the previous study [9] to investigate whether the invasively recorded auditory induced signals can be classified to a clinically acceptable level of accuracy, as the outcome of our previous quality investigation led us to expect [9]. We also wanted to investigate whether the classification accuracies of the invasively recorded CERA data are superior to classification outcomes using data for the standard clinical electrode settings.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Subjects

Data sets for seven subjects were included in the present analysis. The details for all subjects are given

in supplementary table 1 of a previous paper [9]. For this analysis we used data from seven subjects (Epi02, Epi04, Epi05, Epi06, Epi07, Epi09 and Epi10, 45–80 yr, $\bar{\text{age}}=57.4$ yr, 3 × male, 4 × female, 4 × implantation on left side, 3 × implantation on right side, 3 × Cochlear, 2 × MED-EL, 2 × Advanced Bionics). For various reasons, the data for three subjects had to be excluded from analysis: Epi01, slightly different recording settings and no single trial data; Epi03: strong artefacts, epidural electrodes presumably too close to the implant; Epi08: patient had been deaf for a long time, thus no stimulus responses were observable at all. With subject Epi10, unintentional removal of two epidural electrodes occurred during dressing changes, but our classification analysis was nevertheless successfully performed on the remaining epidural electrode.

All participants gave their informed written consent to the study, which was approved by the local ethics committee (approval number 6863) and is in accordance with the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki. The subjects did not receive any payment for participating in the study.

2.2. Data acquisition and experimental procedure

Details of the data acquisition and experimental procedure can be found in supplementary table 2 of a previous paper [9]. We used postoperative CERA data for the present classification analysis. To summarize, a clinical ERA device (Nicolet Synergy EDX, Natus Medical Incorporated, Pleasanton, CA, USA) was used in conjunction with a 1 m sound tube for stimulation and recording. The CI processor was stimulated using tone bursts of different frequencies and intensities. Thus, the stimuli were presented acoustically to the microphone of the CI processor, presenting the stimuli in live speech mode and using the clinical processing (including preprocessing) algorithms. The acoustic stimuli were presented using our clinical rate of 0.5 Hz. The CI processor was programmed with a clinical fitting map optimized prior to each recording session. Therefore, the hearing thresholds and the maximum comfortable levels for each stimulation channel of the implant are individually determined, as are the speech coding strategy and other necessary parameters. We therefore also chose the clinical electrical stimulation rate which usually lies between 900 pps and 2000 pps depending on the brand [24]. It must be mentioned that application of stimuli to a CI sound processor affects calibration, especially when the implant's automatic gain control and input dynamic range are used. Nevertheless, this approach was chosen in order to mimic everyday-life listening situations with CIs as closely as possible. The sound tube was, therefore, not specifically calibrated to the stimuli we used here, but we included the set values of the intensities in dB nHL (normal hearing level) in order to represent differences between the levels.

The recording was carried out for five monopolar channels with three epidural electrodes (cranial anterior, medial and posterior position) and one adhesive electrode (Asmuth GmbH Medizintechnik, Minden, Germany) at the ipsilateral mastoid and one at the contralateral mastoid (M1, M2). For epidural recording, disposable epidural electrodes (AD-Tech Medical Instrument Corporation, Racine, WI, USA) were used. The electrodes were placed over the temporal cortex. Further details on the electrodes and their placement can be found in [9].

In all patients, the electrophysiological recordings were performed ipsilateral to stimulation. If patients had an additional contralateral device, it was switched off for the duration of the measurement and if necessary, the contralateral ear was plugged. Due to the fresh surgical wound, we did not place the (unsterile) earplugs into the ipsilateral ear canal, but application of a head bandage and compress closing the ear canal meant that relevant dampening of the sound took place.

The following parameters for the CERA recordings were set: sampling rate: 1.92 kHz; time base: 500 ms; filter settings: 0.05 Hz (−12 dB/octave high-pass) – 30 Hz (−6 dB/octave low-pass); notch filter on (50 Hz); artefact rejection level: 120 μV ; artefact rejection time: 1 ms; averaging: 50. Other stimulus specifications were as follows: audio type was toneburst; polarity +/−; envelope: Blackman; rise/fall-time: 4 ms; plateau: 1000 ms for 500 Hz stimulus, 500 ms for 1000 Hz and 250 ms for 2000 Hz; stimulus rate: 0.5 s^{-1} ; averaging: 50.

For each patient, CERA recording took place in various sessions (500 Hz, 1000 Hz, and 2000 Hz), with multiple runs at different intensity levels on different days. Given patients' general physical condition so soon after surgery, not all individuals were able to undergo all sessions on one day. Furthermore, the number of possible runs per session performed was influenced by the varying physical conditions of the patients. By the end, all of them had been able to undergo at least two different sessions with two or more runs per session. The patients were instructed to count the number of tones (50 plus) presented during the runs. Due to the automatic online artefact rejection procedure of the Nicolet Synergy EDX system (artefact-afflicted trials being discarded until 50 clean averages are reached; for details see [9]), the number of presented tones differed between the runs. After each run the subjects were asked if they could hear the tones, how loud they subjectively felt the presented tones to be, and how many tones they could count. In five of the seven patients, we were also able to record clear non-perceived runs either by presenting stimuli at below the subjective hearing threshold or by performing an additional 0 dB nHL run. These 0 dB nHL recordings could not be carried out for the other two subjects owing to their limited physical resilience.

2.3. Data preprocessing and classification

The data preprocessing involved has already been described in [9]. Analysis was performed with MATLAB 2015a (The Mathworks, Inc. Natick, Massachusetts, USA) using custom-written tools.

Only those trials presumed to be artefact free were used for the next steps in processing. Therefore, the artefact rejection procedure was set to remove any trials including artefacts above 120 μV , which corresponds to the artefact rejection procedure of the ERA device manufacturer; for details see [9]. This data was downsampled to a sampling rate of 128 Hz and used for classification. Therefore, data segments from 0 to 250 ms after sound presentation (pre-attentive components) were extracted. Finally, single-trial classification (leave-one-out cross-validation) was carried out using shrinkage-regularized linear discriminant analysis (sLDA, [25]) for each channel separately. Each of the classification results (into different perceived intensities or perceived vs. non-perceived runs) was further compared with the actual chance level [26] in order to identify random results. The sLDA approach was chosen, as classifying event-related potentials (ERPs) on a single-trial basis is challenging. As described in a publication by Blankertz *et al* [25], this is due to the high trial-to-trial variability and the unfavourable ratio between signal (ERP) and noise (artefacts and neural background activity). Therefore, use of a suitable classifier is essential. Blankertz *et al* [25] demonstrated that linear discriminant analysis (LDA) is a powerful tool for the classification of ERP components when endowed with shrinkage for use with high dimensional features. This is due to the fact that the classification performance of an LDA classifier crucially depends on accurate estimates of the class means and the common covariance matrix. If enough data is available, making an accurate estimate is not a problem. However, in cases where there is insufficient data - due, for example, to the small number of trials available from patient measurements, or to data being contaminated by outliers [27] - a conventional estimation of the covariance matrix fails. In these cases, the covariance matrix is ill conditioned and there is a risk of overfitting the data when using higher dimensional features. The conditioning of the covariance matrix can now be improved by regularization. An efficient method of regularization is analytic shrinkage regularization, as described in more detail in Blankertz *et al* [25] and Bauernfeind *et al* [28]. Analytic shrinkage regularization compensates for systematic errors caused by a small amount of data. This process, known as analytic shrinkage-regularized LDA (sLDA), is computationally very efficient, outperforming ordinary LDA significantly at low trial-to-feature ratios [13, 25, 27, 28], and is at the same level as more complex classification methods [25, 27, 28]. In this work, we applied the analytic shrinkage calculation as implemented in

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the data acquisition and preprocessing steps. After monopolar recording involving five channels (M1, M2, anterior, medial and posterior), three bipolar derivations (medial-anterior, medial-posterior and posterior-anterior) were calculated offline. Afterwards, channels were corrected for artefacts and downsampled to 128 Hz. In a subsequent step, data segments from 0 to 250 ms after sound presentation (preattentive components) were extracted and used for classification (using sLDA and leave-one-out cross-validation). Finally, trials were also averaged and used to investigate significant differences in the induced AEPs. Modified from [9].

BCILAB [29] and used for AEP sLDA classification in healthy subjects and patients [11, 13, 28].

Independent of our classification investigation, we performed a visual inspection of the induced AEPs. Therefore, the preprocessed trials were also averaged for each channel over single runs to investigate significant differences. To this end, confidence intervals with significance level $\alpha = 5\%$ were estimated using bootstrapping based on $n = 1000$ bootstrap samples [13, 15]. The procedure as a whole is visually depicted by means of a schematic illustration in figure 2.

2.4. Speech perception with CIs

As part of our standard clinical CI evaluation procedures, pure-tone audiometry and speech perception tests are performed [30]. Pure-tone audiometric measurements are carried out using an audiometer of type AD2117 (previously designated AD17 and AD2017) manufactured by Audio-DATA GmbH, Duvensee, Germany. The stimuli are calibrated to hearing level (HL) and presented using headphones (HDA300, previously designated HDA200, Sennheiser electronic GmbH & Co. KG, Wedemark, Germany) and bone conductors (KLH96, Westra Elektroakustik GmbH, Binswangen, Germany). Speech perception tests after surgery are performed using free-field loudspeakers in front of the patient at a distance of 1 m from their head. Depending on residual hearing on the ipsi- and contralateral side, different recording conditions are applied. In this way, it is determined whether the residual acoustic

hearing is relevant and can contribute to speech perception (i.e. if the behavioural threshold is better than around 95 dB HL [30]). Testing can, for example, be performed with and without an acoustic component/hearing aid. Furthermore, the ear canal can be closed (using an earplug, for example) if so required, or left open. In individual cases (e.g. when the residual hearing on the contralateral side is too good for correct plugging), the stimuli are presented to the CI processor by means of a direct audio cable connection. Speech perception is measured using the Freiburg Polysyllabic Numbers Test, the Freiburg Monosyllables Test (both in quiet at a presentation level of 65 dB SPL, sound pressure level, [31]), and the Hochmair-Desoyer/Schulz/Moser sentence test in quiet (presentation level at 65 dB SPL) and CCITT speech-shaped noise (10 dB signal-to-noise ratio, SNR) [32].

3. Results

For the CERA classification, we investigated two different conditions: (a) single-trial classification accuracies into different perceived intensities and (b) classification into perceived vs. non-perceived (below the hearing threshold or 0 dB nHL) runs.

3.1. Classification accuracies into differently perceived (i.e. soft/loud) intensities

In all seven subjects, single-trial classification results were significantly above the random level for sounds of different intensities for at least one of the

eight channels (M1, M2, anterior, medial, posterior, medial-anterior, medial-posterior and posterior-anterior).

As an example, figure 3 shows the classification outcomes of patient Epi05 for CERA 1000 Hz recordings from day 2. The values in this figure represent the mean classification accuracies over all cross-validation folds. By way of an overview, table 1 gives the highest achieved recording-specific classification results for the seven patients. The maximum accuracies for the individual subjects were between 68.3% (Epi09, CERA 1000 Hz/day 2/monopolar posterior/90 dB nHL vs. 70 dB nHL) and 89.1% (Epi07; CERA 1000/day 2/bipolar posterior-anterior/90 dB nHL vs. 60 dB nHL). When considering the different types of recording (monopolar

surface electrodes, monopolar and bipolar epidural leads), the highest classification accuracies (89.1%) were achieved for bipolar epidural leads. For monopolar surface electrodes (M1 and M2), classification accuracies of up to 68% (Epi05, CERA 1000 Hz/day 2/M2/100 dB nHL vs. 60 dB nHL) were achieved.

3.2. Classification accuracies into perceived and non-perceived tones

In five (Epi04, Epi05, Epi06, Epi09 and Epi10) of the seven CERA subjects, it proved possible to perform additional classification analyses comparing 'perceived' and 'non-perceived' sounds (table 2). The highest individual accuracies achieved were between 72.8% (Epi09, CERA 2000 Hz/day 2/monopolar posterior/60 dB nHL vs. 0 dB nHL) and 99.2%

Table 1. Highest achieved recording and session-specific classification accuracies into perceived intensities (with leave-one-out cross-validation) for all patients. All results better than random [26] are designated in **bold**. Highest session-specific results are further indicated in *italics*.

Subj.	Freq. (Hz)	Day	M1			M2			Anterior			Medial			Posterior			Med.-Ant.			Med.-Post.			Post.-Ant.		
			Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Max. Subj. (%)	
Epi02	1000	2	49	90vs80	47	90vs80	48	90vs80	55	90vs80	58	90vs80	64	<i>90vs80</i>	48	90vs80	43,9	90vs80	43,9	90vs80	43,9	90vs80	43,9	90vs80	74	
	500	1	53	95vs90	54	95vs80	56	95vs90	57	95vs80	60	95vs80	55,6	95vs80	53	95vs80	47	95vs80	47	95vs80	47	95vs80	47	95vs80	74	
	500	2	56	90vs80	57	90vs80	59	90vs80	54	90vs80	74	<i>90vs80</i>	44,3	90vs80	53,1	90vs80	56	90vs80	56	90vs80	56	90vs80	56	90vs80	74	
Epi04	2000	1	42,5	70vs50	55,7	60vs50	65,5	70vs50	69,6	<i>70vs50</i>	75,9	<i>70vs50</i>	78,3	<i>70vs50</i>	59,8	70vs50	77,5	<i>70vs50</i>	77,5	<i>70vs50</i>	77,5	<i>70vs50</i>	77,5	<i>70vs50</i>	78,3	
	1000	1	45	90vs80	50	90vs80	61	90vs80	60	90vs80	59,6	90vs80	65,5	<i>90vs80</i>	44,2	90vs80	49,6	90vs80	44,2	90vs80	49,6	90vs80	49,6	90vs80	78,3	
	500	1	57	110vs100	56	110vs100	59,8	110vs100	70,8	<i>110vs100</i>	69,6	<i>110vs100</i>	76,9	<i>110vs100</i>	64,6	<i>110vs100</i>	71,6	<i>110vs100</i>	64,6	<i>110vs100</i>	71,6	<i>110vs100</i>	71,6	<i>110vs100</i>	78,3	
Epi05	2000	1	49	60vs50	52,5	60vs50	48,7	60vs50	59,1	60vs50	48,2	60vs50	54,9	60vs50	54,3	60vs50	50,5	60vs50	54,3	60vs50	50,5	60vs50	50,5	60vs50	84,8	
	2000	2	46,1	60vs50	49	60vs50	45,1	60vs50	53,7	60vs50	54,3	60vs50	61	60vs50	62,4	60vs50	54	60vs50	62,4	60vs50	54	60vs50	54	60vs50	84,8	
	1000	1	60,2	80vs60	58	80vs60	58,8	70vs60	60,8	80vs60	64,5	80vs70	60,2	80vs60	55,9	70vs60	64,4	<i>70vs60</i>	64,4	<i>70vs60</i>	64,4	<i>70vs60</i>	64,4	<i>70vs60</i>	84,8	
	1000	2	63,7	<i>100vs50</i>	68	<i>100vs60</i>	76,7	<i>80vs40</i>	84,8	<i>80vs40</i>	64,9	<i>100vs40</i>	79,2	<i>100vs40</i>	71	<i>100vs40</i>	76,5	<i>100vs40</i>	76,5	<i>100vs40</i>	76,5	<i>100vs40</i>	76,5	<i>100vs40</i>	84,8	
	500	1	53	90vs80	52	90vs70	61,3	100vs80	61,1	100vs90	63,1	80vs70	56	100vs70	66,4	<i>90vs80</i>	60,4	90vs70	66,4	<i>90vs80</i>	60,4	90vs70	66,4	<i>90vs80</i>	84,8	
	500	2	58,8	100vs80	48	100vs90	50,6	100vs80	58,9	90vs80	64,9	<i>100vs90</i>	61,9	100vs80	62,6	100vs80	68,2	<i>100vs80</i>	68,2	<i>100vs80</i>	68,2	<i>100vs80</i>	68,2	<i>100vs80</i>	84,8	
Epi06 ^a	2000	1	60,6	60vs50	53,1	60vs50	53,1	60vs50	56,2	70vs60	54,9	70vs60	54	60vs50	48,5	70vs50	66,7	<i>60vs50</i>	66,7	<i>60vs50</i>	66,7	<i>60vs50</i>	66,7	<i>60vs50</i>	76,3	
	2000	2	n.a.	n.a.	40,4	70vs60	51	70vs60	52,5	70vs60	48,5	70vs60	41,6	70vs60	48,5	70vs60	42,3	70vs60	42,3	70vs60	42,3	70vs60	42,3	70vs60	76,3	
	1000	1	50	90vs80	51,5	95vs80	61,1	95vs70	56,5	95vs70	60,2	90vs70	73,2	<i>95vs70</i>	53,2	95vs70	69,6	<i>80vs70</i>	69,6	<i>80vs70</i>	69,6	<i>80vs70</i>	69,6	<i>80vs70</i>	76,3	
	1000	2	50	90vs80	50,5	90vs80	58,8	90vs80	58,3	90vs80	59,8	90vs80	53,6	80vs70	53,2	90vs70	53,6	90vs70	53,6	90vs70	53,6	90vs70	53,6	90vs70	76,3	
	500	1	56	80vs70	55,6	90vs80	62,4	90vs70	65,3	<i>90vs80</i>	64	80vs70	73,3	<i>90vs70</i>	59,8	90vs80	76,3	<i>90vs70</i>	76,3	<i>90vs70</i>	76,3	<i>90vs70</i>	76,3	<i>90vs70</i>	76,3	
	500	2	54	90vs80	50,5	90vs70	51,4	90vs70	47,7	90vs80	49,1	90vs70	68,6	<i>90vs70</i>	63,1	<i>90vs70</i>	64,7	<i>90vs70</i>	64,7	<i>90vs70</i>	64,7	<i>90vs70</i>	64,7	<i>90vs70</i>	76,3	
Epi07	2000	1	54	70vs60	54,9	80vs50	52,2	70vs60	54,4	60vs50	53,3	80vs50	62,7	<i>80vs50</i>	57,4	80vs60	61,7	<i>80vs60</i>	61,7	<i>80vs60</i>	61,7	<i>80vs60</i>	61,7	<i>80vs60</i>	89,1	
	2000	2	63	50vs30	60,8	60vs40	59,6	80vs30	63,3	<i>70vs30</i>	80	<i>80vs30</i>	70,3	<i>80vs30</i>	78,6	<i>60vs30</i>	77,4	<i>80vs30</i>	77,4	<i>80vs30</i>	77,4	<i>80vs30</i>	77,4	<i>80vs30</i>	89,1	
	1000	1	52	100vs80	52,4	100vs80	55,5	100vs90	50,7	90vs80	54,6	100vs90	58,7	100vs90	65,2	100vs90	57,6	100vs90	65,2	100vs90	57,6	100vs90	57,6	100vs90	89,1	
	1000	2	54	80vs60	65	90vs60	58,9	80vs60	62,2	90vs60	75,3	<i>100vs60</i>	78,5	<i>80vs60</i>	82,1	<i>90vs60</i>	89,1	<i>90vs60</i>	89,1	<i>90vs60</i>	89,1	<i>90vs60</i>	89,1	<i>90vs60</i>	89,1	
	500	1	52,5	100vs80	57,4	110vs80	60,4	100vs80	66,3	<i>110vs80</i>	75,4	<i>110vs80</i>	67,8	<i>110vs90</i>	76,5	<i>110vs80</i>	71,4	<i>110vs80</i>	71,4	<i>110vs80</i>	71,4	<i>110vs80</i>	71,4	<i>110vs80</i>	89,1	

(Continued.)

Table 1. (Continued.)

Subj.	Freq. (Hz)	Day	M1			M2			Anterior			Medial			Posterior			Med.-Ant.			Med.-Post.			Post.-Ant.		
			Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Max. Subj. (%)											
Epi09	2000	2	61	40vs30	60.2	40vs30	56.4	40vs30	58.8	50vs30	55.1	60vs40	56.5	60vs30	51.8	50vs30	46.8	50vs30	68.3		50vs30	46.8	50vs30	68.3		
	1000	1	50	80vs70	62.4	80vs70	62	80vs70	56	80vs70	62	80vs70	55.1	80vs70	48.3	80vs70	43	80vs70		80vs70	43	80vs70				
	1000	2	64	90vs70	58	90vs70	56.3	90vs70	64.6	90vs70	68.3	90vs70	58.7	90vs70	56.6	90vs70	50	90vs70		90vs70	50	90vs70				
Epi10 ^b	2000	1	56.3	60vs50	57	60vs50	n.a.	n.a.	71.2	70vs50	N.n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	na.	n.a.	n.a.	71.4		na.	n.a.	n.a.	71.4		
	1000	1	64	100vs70	61	100vs70	n.a.	n.a.	67.7	90vs70	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	na.	n.a.	n.a.		n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.			
	500	1	61	110vs90	67	110vs90	n.a.	n.a.	71.4	100vs90	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	na.	n.a.	n.a.		n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.			
Max. Pos. (%)			64		68	68	76.7	84.8	80	79.2	82.1	89.1														

^a Electrode M1 disconnected during CERA 2000 Hz recording on day 2.

^b Anterior and posteriorepidural electrodes separated over the weekend.

Table 2. Highest achieved recording and session-specific classification accuracies into perceived and non-perceived intensities (with leave-one-out cross-validation) for five (Epi04, Epi05, Epi06, Epi09 and Epi10) patients. All results better than random [26] are designated in **bold**. Highest session-specific results are further indicated in *italics*.

Subj.	Freq. (Hz)	Day	M1			M2			Anterior			Medial			Posterior			Med.-Ant.			Med.-Post.			Post.-Ant.			Max. Subj. (%)
			Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Acc. (%)	Vol. (dB nHL)	Vol. (dB nHL)	
Epi04	2000	1	67.3	60vs40	70.4	60vs40	79.8	70vs40	86.4	70vs40	95.5	70vs40	98.3	70vs40	91.7	70vs40	99.2	70vs40	99.2	70vs40	99.2	70vs40	99.2	70vs40	99.2	70vs40	99.2
	1000	1	68	80vs70	68.4	80vs70	85	90vs70	77.2	90vs70	85	90vs70	93.8	80vs70	83.9	80vs70	92.1	80vs70	92.1	90vs70	92.1	90vs70	92.1	90vs70	92.1	90vs70	92.1
	500	1	72	110vs80	67	110vs80	78.4	100vs80	90.4	110vs80	94.1	110vs80	96.9	110vs80	85.5	100vs80	98.5	100vs80	98.5	110vs80	98.5	110vs80	98.5	110vs80	110vs80	98.5	
Epi05	2000	2	51.5	60vs0	52	50vs0	66.2	60vs0	67	60vs0	52.9	60vs0	69.6	50vs0	55.3	60vs0	62.2	60vs0	62.2	60vs0	62.2	60vs0	62.2	60vs0	60vs0	60vs0	60vs0
	1000	1	63	80vs0	49	80vs0	61.6	70vs0	71.9	80vs0	77.5	80vs0	71.6	80vs0	64.1	80vs0	66.4	80vs0	66.4	80vs0	66.4	80vs0	66.4	80vs0	80vs0	80vs0	80vs0
	500	2	52.9	80vs60	54.5	90vs60	59.5	90vs60	69.9	90vs60	65.9	90vs60	67.3	90vs60	66.3	100vs60	67.9	100vs60	67.9	100vs60	67.9	100vs60	67.9	100vs60	100vs60	100vs60	100vs60
Epi06	500	1	58	80vs0	54.5	80vs0	55.6	80vs0	57	80vs0	58.1	70vs0	67.6	90vs0	67.3	90vs0	75.2	90vs0	75.2	90vs0	75.2	90vs0	75.2	90vs0	90vs0	90vs0	75.2
Epi09	2000	2	61.4	50vs0	61.4	60vs0	63.4	60vs0	66.3	60vs0	72.8	60vs0	56.9	30vs0	53.5	40vs0	51.3	40vs0	51.3	40vs0	51.3	40vs0	51.3	40vs0	40vs0	40vs0	40vs0
Epi10 ^a	1000	1	67.4	80vs60	67.3	80vs60	57.1	80vs60	64.4	80vs60	56.4	80vs60	53.5	80vs60	60	80vs60	53	80vs60	53	80vs60	53	80vs60	53	80vs60	70vs60	70vs60	70vs60
	2000	1	65.4	70vs0	67	60vs0	N.a.	N.a.	70.1	70vs0	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.
	1000	1	74.5	100vs50	77	100vs50	N.a.	N.a.	79.6	80vs50	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.
	500	1	70	110vs80	64.6	110vs80	N.a.	N.a.	71.3	110vs80	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.
Max. Pos. (%)			74.5		77	85		90.4		95.5		98.3		91.7		99.2		99.2		99.2		99.2					

^a Epidural electrodes anterior and posterior separated over the weekend.

Table 3. Speech perception test results at the end of the first fitting week. Residual hearing was considered to be relevant if the behavioural threshold was better than around 95 dB HL. In no case did contralateral hearing contribute, as the patients were deaf on that side or the ear canal was adequately closed and the hearing device was switched off.

	Ipsilateral residual hearing during electrophys. recordings (first days after surg.)	Measurement condition for speech tests	Ipsilateral residual hearing for speech tests (five weeks after surg.)	Polysyll. (Freiburg Numbers) as % correct	Freiburg Monosyll. as % correct	HSM sentence test in quiet as % correct	HSM sentence test in noise 10 dB SNR as % correct
Epi02	Not relevant	Free-field	Not relevant	100	90	95.25	50
Epi04	Not relevant	Free-field	Not relevant	100	90	95.28	95.28
Epi05	Not relevant	Free-field	Not relevant	100	70	88.67	19.81
Epi06	Not relevant	Free-field	Not relevant	100	20	50	10.37
Epi07 ^a	Not contrib.	Free-field	Amplified	100	65	97.47	71.69
Epi09	Not relevant	Free-field	Not relevant	90	40	55.66	7.54
Epi10 ^a	Not contrib.	Cable conn.	Not applicable	100	50	59.43	16.03

surg.—surgery, Polysyll.—Polysyllables, Monosyll.—Monosyllables, contrib.—contributing, conn.—connection.

^a In both patients the ipsilateral behavioural threshold dropped postoperatively due to liquid in the middle ear which was resolved at the first fitting week. Additional dampening was achieved due to the head bandage.

(Epi04, CERA 2000/day1/bipolar posterior-anterior/70 dB nHL vs. 40 dB nHL). Figure 4 shows the classification results of patient Epi04 for CERA 1000 Hz recordings on day 1. As with the perceived sounds, the highest classification accuracies were achieved for epidural recordings. However, even for the monopolar surface electrodes, classification accuracies of up to 77% (Epi10, CERA 1000 Hz/day 1/M2/100 dB nHL vs. 50 dB nHL) were again achieved.

3.3. Speech perception with CIs

The speech perception data with CI at the end of the first fitting week (five weeks after surgery) is presented in table 3. Figure 5 compares the outcome of a speech test in noise with the loudness difference required to obtain the best classification results. In all cases, the test set-up for the electrophysiological recordings was designed such that only the recently implanted CI contributed to hearing; this was achieved by switching off contralateral devices

and plugging or dampening acoustic hearing. Five weeks later, in speech perception tests, in six of the seven cases it was again ensured that only the recently implanted CI contributed. However, in Epi07 the ipsilateral residual hearing after surgery was massively dampened (this presumably being caused by remaining liquid in the middle ear, as well as by dampening due to the head bandage and compress). Therefore, we assume that in this case the sole contributor to hearing was the implant. At the time of the first fitting week the residual hearing had recovered significantly, and the speech perception tests were performed in free-field, even with acoustic amplification of the residual hearing. Thus, during this recording both acoustic hearing and the CI contributed to the test results.

4. Discussion

In the present study we investigated data on invasively recorded auditory evoked potentials and standard clinical recordings in CI users. The aim of this analysis was twofold: to get one step nearer to closing the auditory loop, and automatic fitting in a manner feasible for use in everyday-life situations. The first aspect may allow CI recipients in the future to passively and actively control their implant by means of brain signals. The second aspect will help to improve clinical fitting - especially in children and toddlers, which is currently extremely time-consuming and laborious - as well as within rural areas where experienced audiologists are too far away to carry out follow-up.

The main emphasis of our investigations described in this paper was on the suitability of our results for classification purposes. Therefore, we calculated the classification accuracy into perceived and non-perceived trials, as well as into soft and loud

trials. However, an important limitation was the sub-optimal paradigm available for the classification studies. As already mentioned, a Nicolet Synergy EDX system was used to generate all stimuli and to record the evoked potentials. This device was chosen as it is our standard clinical system for evaluation of hearing by means of AEPs. The focus of our work was on the easy applicability of the method, not only for the patients in everyday life, but also for the department/centre using it. Most otolaryngology departments/centres are able to perform CERA, but usually the recording of P300 requires expensive additional modules or even additional devices. This paper is concerned with measurements made under typical clinical conditions rather than optimum laboratory conditions. That is also why we chose acoustic stimulation of the CI processor operating in live speech mode. Furthermore, due to their general state of health, not all patients were able to undergo all sessions. Thus, there are inadequacies in terms of what the subsequent statistical evaluation can show. Nevertheless, despite the above-mentioned limiting requirements and restrictions, we were able to achieve promising results. By selecting an optimal recording electrode configuration for each subject, in all cases but one (Epi09) we exceeded classification accuracies of 70%, which are considered as the limit for practical usefulness in BCIs [33, 34]. However, the best electrode configuration varied across our subjects and there were also many conditions where the classification results were only slightly above - or even below - chance level. Nevertheless, we attained these accuracies using a set-up which is available at most otolaryngology departments/centres without the need for further investment. Where laboratory conditions are ideal, the achieved classification accuracy will naturally be higher.

Of course, classification accuracy would also improve if the background activity relating to ERP data was attenuated by averaging multiple trials of recorded signals in order to obtain a higher signal-to-noise ratio. However, this method suffers from two main drawbacks [35]. Collecting data from multiple trials is time-consuming and delays the BCI response. Moreover, latency distortions may appear in the averaged result due to variable time-locking of the ERPs in the individual trials. Thus, the advantages and disadvantages have to be weighed. If the achieved results are sufficient with single-trial data, however, this approach would be preferable.

In children, it could be necessary to use more trials. A further challenge with CERA measurements in younger individuals is ensuring the child is in a state where they are attentive, but not restless. Single-trial AEPs will still be subject to movement artefact. Classification of data obtained when the child was restless would yield invalid results. This still remains to be investigated, however.

A question that also arises is whether similar outcomes could also be achieved by means of less invasive recording methods. A non-invasive approach such as conventional EEG works fairly well, but has major disadvantages in terms of everyday-life applicability [9, 20]. For example, the electrodes would have to be mounted and removed on a daily basis, which is time-consuming. Furthermore, the electrodes would remain on the skin throughout the day, which is uncomfortable for the patient. There may also be problems with sweating, so that the device may have to be removed during exercise. In the event of an electrode shifting, or where it is necessary to re-mount electrodes during the day, the patient would also need to have skin preparation and electrode gel on them at all times. Moreover, external EEG electrodes would be externally visible, which is something many patients do not like. It may thus be beneficial if the electrodes which are in place anyway can be used for recording.

Nourski *et al* carried out recordings with a bilateral CI recipient who had an implanted, subdural electrode grid due to epilepsy [36]. They stimulated the CI processor acoustically and found clear responses that resembled typical AEP responses (e.g. clear morphology, increasing amplitude and decreasing latency with higher stimulation level, as well as stability over time). Thus, this approach yielded promising results, but of course the intention is that patients without epilepsy should also benefit from closed-loop CI systems. A more realistic approach would be the use of existing CI electrodes. Here, the external reference electrode would be the electrode of choice as it is, during surgery, placed under the temporal muscle onto the bone close to the temporal lobe, which is a promising location for recording cortical potentials. One approach is to directly control this electrode using the telemetric connection between the CI processor via the coil and

the implant. This was investigated by McLaughlin *et al* [37], who recorded auditory brainstem responses (ABRs) as well as performing CERA, and were able to find clear response waves. Nevertheless, they stimulated the implant electrically resulting in limited applicability to everyday-life listening. Furthermore, due to hardware limitations of the integrated electronic components, signal processing and transmitting times between coil and implant, the recordings are currently too slow for real-time applications.

Somers *et al* remedied this problem by installing a temporary percutaneous connection to the CI electrodes in three patients. Here, several electrode constellations were tested [38]. Depending on electrode position and recording setup, the authors found clear waves in both the ABR and CERA responses. The waves also showed typical characteristics of auditory responses, with decreasing amplitudes and increasing latencies associated with decreasing stimulation levels. Thus, good potentials can also be recorded in a recording location between temporal muscle and bone. We must qualify this by stating that these recordings were made with quiet patients in laboratory conditions. In everyday-life applications, we would expect far more artefacts caused by head movements and muscle contractions. This should definitely be investigated. Furthermore, this group also stimulated the implant electrically resulting in limited applicability to everyday-life listening. Another advantage of our more invasive approach relates to power consumption. As the skull dampens electrical fields in the brain, intracranially recorded potentials are larger and need less gain, thus consuming less power [38], which is a relevant issue in everyday-life listening situations with CIs. Of course, in continuing with the epidural approach and developing electrodes which are connected to the CI, the design of these recording electrodes must be developed with great care to be safe for clinical work. Electrodes must be designed to be perfectly smooth, partly with a view to possible later explantation of the CI. And it goes without saying that the surgeon must have the requisite expertise, which is of course essential in this aspect as in all other aspects of cochlear implantation.

When looking at the conditions which are typically best for classification, it is noticeable that the required loudness differences vary between patients. To give an example, in patient Epi05 the best classification accuracy is reached where the loudness difference is 100 dB nHL vs. 40 dB nHL for classifying different intensities (loud vs. soft), whereas for patient Epi02 a smaller difference (90 dB nHL vs. 80 dB nHL) appears to be sufficient. Interestingly, this would seem to correspond to speech perception with CIs in noise at the end of the first fitting week. Epi05 was able to perceive 19.81% correctly in the HSM test in noise (10 dB SNR), whereas Epi02 performed far better, perceiving 50% correct in the same test. This relation appears to be the case

for all patients except Epi07, who needed large loudness differences for classification, but performed well in the speech test in noise. However, as mentioned in the section 3, for the epidural recording we can be certain that only the CI contributed to hearing, but at the end of the first fitting week the (remarkable) residual hearing was even acoustically amplified by means of a hearing aid. So, unfortunately for this patient, the data sets are not comparable. Technical parameters of the CI, such as automatic gain control (AGC) and input dynamic range (IDR), may also be contributing to these differences, but confirming this influence would necessitate more data. Classification of perceived vs. non-perceived tones would require a new, more systematic investigation since, in some of the subjects, we went below the subjective hearing threshold for recording the non-perceived tones, and in some individuals we carried out a 0 dB nHL recording, depending on the condition of the patient so soon after surgery. Unfortunately, this prevents comparability. Nevertheless, these relations merit thorough future investigation. Other research groups have also reported promising relations between electrophysiological recordings and speech perception in noise. Han and Dimitrijevic, for example, recorded acoustic change complexes (ACCs); this involves investigating by means of EEG whether or not the subject can detect the change in a stimulus, and how different the stimuli have to be. They used amplitude-modulated sounds with CI subjects and normal-hearing controls [39]. Gransier *et al* recorded electrically evoked phenomena called auditory steady-state responses (eASSRs), which measure the ability of the auditory pathway to encode temporal envelope modulations. They hypothesized that degenerative processes in the auditory pathway are one of the reasons for the high variances in CI performance, and indeed found strong correlations between the eASSR recordings and speech perception in noise [40]. Thus, electrophysiological correlates indeed seem to correspond to speech perception in noise. Particularly if it could be corroborated that the potential classification of different loudness intensities (which would be obtained for the fitting in any case) also corresponds to speech perception abilities in noise, this would open up new possibilities for CI fitting in uncooperative patients such as children.

In clinical audiometry, CERA can be used to objectively determine the functionality of the auditory system. In this case, P100 and N100 components of the AEPs are used to evaluate the auditory processing chain and the functionality of the auditory cortex. The drawback of these and other cortical potentials in clinical applications is the long measurement time (including preparation). This is strenuous for patients, and consumes a large amount of valuable clinical resources, including staff time and a test cubicle which is thus made otherwise unavailable for further uses.

For our classification investigation, we therefore focused - as a first step - on data obtained from the CERA recordings. More specifically, we used AEP data segments between 0 and 250 ms after sound presentation (preattentive components). The main reason why we chose the preattentive components for this classification analysis was their suitability for estimating stimulus response thresholds higher up in the auditory pathway than is the case with compound action potentials (CAPs) or ABRs. Therefore, we obtained data on perceived and non-perceived stimuli. We also investigated differences between soft and loud sensations, as this provides valuable information on above-threshold behaviour, including the dynamic range of an individual's hearing. In our first investigation reported in [9], we also found clear N100 waves in all cases. For the epidural electrodes, the N100 were also visible at lower stimulation intensities than with scalp electrodes. However, this result was to be expected as the electrodes are closer to the signal source (the auditory N100 being generated in the primary and association auditory cortices in the superior temporal gyrus), and the signal is not dampened by the skull.

Particularly in children and toddlers, achieving adequate fitting is a very challenging task, as these patients are not able to give detailed feedback and it is difficult to control their attention for behavioural tests. Thus, an easily applicable, rapid and objective evaluation method would be extremely helpful. The main objective recording methods currently established involve measurement of electrically evoked compound action potentials (ECAPs), electrically evoked stapedial reflex thresholds (ESRTs, only intra-operatively recorded) and electrically evoked auditory brainstem responses (EABRs). These methods yield only very limited information on the dynamic range of electrical hearing, and no information on cortical processing. For cortical recordings, however, the patient usually has to be quiet and attentive for a long time, and achieving this is extremely challenging in children. With implanted electrodes the preparation time is negligible, and if the required information can be obtained from single-trial data, the intrinsic recording time will also be very short. Thus, if classification into perceived and non-perceived stimuli - and perhaps even into soft and loud stimuli - can be performed to clinically acceptable accuracy with a single-trial recording based on implanted electrodes, a quick and reliable evaluation of the fitting could be possible. As our classification analyses lead to a classification accuracy of above 70%, which is considered the limit for practical usefulness in BCIs [33, 34], our results clearly demonstrate the usefulness of the approach.

The data in the present study was, of course, obtained in adults and cannot be applied directly to children. This approach is still, however, at an early stage. For a classifier such as the one applied

here, some training data is required where it is known whether the individual patient can differentiate between perceived and non-perceived tones. In adults, this is generally fairly easy to obtain, whereas in children and toddlers it is more challenging. Based on our experience, however, it is nevertheless possible in most cases. Under the approach to rehabilitation adopted at our department, a therapist and an engineer work together to carry out CI fitting in toddlers, with the engineer responsible for technical aspects and the therapist closely watching the child. Here, in most instances an experienced therapist is able to determine whether the child can hear something or not. But even where this is not the case, Finke *et al* [11] report that a cross-subject classifier without individual data training is also possible, has been well researched in machine learning and has already been applied in BCI approaches. Use could also be made of other (e.g. visual or tactile) modalities [11]. We are, therefore, optimistic that this challenge can be met in the future, and that, with ongoing research conducted over a long timescale, this approach can also be applied in children. And, if this approach becomes widely adopted, there could be enough data to develop a general classifier at some point in the future. Naturally, however, this is a long-term vision.

Moreover, when considering self-fitting applications where the CI is fitted automatically (perhaps without an audiologist present on site), automatic classification into perceived and non-perceived stimuli - or even into soft and loud stimuli - would be a breakthrough. This would be advantageous in poorer countries where, in many cases, no experienced audiologist is available for fitting, or in rural areas where the nearest one is still far away. Here, the patient and the audiologist can only be connected using telehealth solutions, which always makes communication more difficult. Furthermore, it would be helpful if the automatic fitting procedure could be carried out independently so that the audiologist could concentrate on the patient. Furthermore, in more developed countries it is often the case that the fitting engineer does not use all possible parameters that could be adjusted in the clinical fitting software. A possible approach towards automatic fitting procedures is that a target measure is defined - a speech perception score, for example. A patient's current speech perception score is measured and, based on the difference between current and target perception, fitting parameters such as threshold level, maximum comfortable level and other parameters are adjusted. The fitting algorithm decides which of these parameters are changed, and by how much. The speech perception score of the patient is measured again, and the whole procedure is repeated until speech perception is at a maximum level. An evaluation with nine experienced adult patients shows that there are differences between the clinical map and the automatically

fitted map, but altogether the outcome would seem to be comparable [41]. The approach presented in our work here would be helpful, especially in cases where no speech perception score can be measured. This automatic fitting approach would also allow a large number of different speech coding algorithms to be tested in a systematic way. Use of learning algorithms would make possible self-optimization of speech processing for each patient and for different listening situations. The requirements concerning safety and reliability for self-fitting systems are, of course, very stringent, and it must be ensured that no overstimulation occurs at any time. Nevertheless, at this point in time, the performance of the system would not be sufficiently reliable for a closed-loop control system adjusting the cochlear implant fitting, so there is still work to be done in this regard.

Event-related potentials such as mismatch negativity (MMN) and P300 are later components which are related to higher cognitive processes. Therefore, they are used to evaluate deficits at this cortical level, including discrimination between different entities of tones, examples being frequency, pitch, loudness levels and speaker discrimination. These later components play a key role in closing the auditory loop [10–12]. In our first study [9], we also recorded P300 and MMN as an oddball paradigm with different pitches, but the scope for data analysis regarding P300 and MMN in our clinical ERA devices is limited. Therefore, the next step will involve recording of later components with epidural electrodes, using a full EEG device, in a new study currently in preparation.

5. Conclusion

In this study we explored the possibility of using invasively recorded preattentive AEPs in seven CI users for single-channel, single-trial classification analyses. It was generally possible to achieve good classification accuracy into sound perceived and not perceived when the best-performing electrodes were selected. Classifying different levels of sound stimulation accurately proved more challenging and, in many conditions, provided classification results which were only slightly above or even below chance level. Nevertheless, the required differences in loudness level appeared to correspond to speech perception in noise.

Our study shows that the approach presented has promise, but at this point in time classification accuracy would not be sufficient to allow closed-loop control of cochlear implant programming. Further refinement of methods is clearly still required to improve accuracy. However, with the procedures adopted here we are taking steps towards developing potential next-generation automatic fitting approaches, especially with respect to the applicability of closed auditory loops in everyday life.

Data availability statement

No new data were created or analysed in this study.

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Conflict of interest

Authors declare no conflict of interests.

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